

A Lightweight Convolutional Neural Network for Real-time Tomato Leaf Disease Detection

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Abstract: Tomato leaf diseases significantly impact crop yield and threaten global food security, particularly in resource-constrained regions with limited access to diagnostic tools. This research introduces an optimised and efficient disease identification framework comparing a streamlined custom convolutional neural network (CNN) with the larger VGG16 model. Both models were trained and validated on 6,124 high-resolution images of tomato leaves representing five categories (Bacterial Spot, Early Blight, Yellow Leaf Curl Virus, Mosaic Virus, and healthy specimens). Both models underwent extensive preprocessing and data augmentation techniques to enhance the model's robustness. Experimental results demonstrated that the custom CNN achieved a classification accuracy of 96.9% and a macro F1-score of 0.97, significantly outperforming the performance of 92.8% accuracy and 0.93 F1-score. The custom CNN model demonstrated a remarkable strength in identifying Early Blight and Yellow Leaf Curl Virus. With only 136,000 trainable parameters fewer than VGG16's 14.9 million, the model enables real-time deployment on mobile and Internet of Things (IoT) devices with limited computational resources. This lightweight system has a wide range of applications, including instant disease diagnosis for farmers and precision agriculture through drone or sensor-based monitoring embedded in smart greenhouses for real-time monitoring. These findings demonstrate that a proposed lightweight architecture offers superior performance and scalability for agricultural artificial intelligence applications, providing an accessible, low-cost, edge-compatible solution for tomato disease identification and monitoring for smallholder farmers.

Keywords: Tomato Leaf disease, Lightweight CNN, VGG16, Deep Learning, Precision agriculture, Plant Pathology, Edge AI, Transfer Learning

1. Introduction

Agriculture contributes approximately 23% to Nigeria's gross domestic product (GDP) and remains a critical source of livelihood for millions of farmers [1]. However, agricultural productivity faces significant challenges from pests and diseases, with tomato production experiencing particularly severe threats. Statistics indicate that disease outbreaks have caused 80-100% depreciation in tomato production, highlighting the urgent need for effective disease management strategies [2]. Traditional disease detection methods rely heavily on visual inspection, a process that is often subjective, time-consuming, and prone to errors, particularly in the early stages of disease development. Agricultural disease detection faces fundamental challenges: the need for real-time monitoring, accurate threat identification, and automated response capabilities. In agriculture, threats manifest as plant diseases caused by pathogens such as fungi, bacteria, and viruses, leading to reduced yields and quality.

The study in [3] improved recognition accuracy by introducing hybrid MobileNetV2-SVM models with

mobile deployment, achieving 96.81% accuracy and real-time treatment recommendations. The study [4] examined methods to enhance agricultural diagnostics using transfer learning, showing that DenseNet outperforms shallow networks with 95.31% accuracy. According to a study [5], lightweight CNNs like LeNet enable disease detection with minimal computational overhead, making them suitable for edge devices. The study [6] proposed a segmentation-based CNN architecture that achieved 98.6% accuracy by training on isolated leaf regions, thereby demonstrating the value of preprocessing. The research [7] investigated hybrid CNN-SVM ensembles for banana leaf disease, achieving 99% accuracy but facing deployment complexity in field conditions.

The paper [8] introduced a ResNet-50 model modified with Leaky-ReLU and 11×11 kernels, achieving 98.3% accuracy, demonstrating that architectural tuning enhances domain-specific performance. The study [9] suggested data

augmentation and transfer learning as critical for generalisation, with ResNet-50 achieving 97% accuracy on augmented datasets. Recent agricultural AI approaches include real-time mobile apps, offline model compression, and multi-disease recommender systems [10]. The study [11] explored the potential of generative adversarial networks (GANs) to mitigate data scarcity in tomato disease datasets, improving model robustness. The study [12] proposed an improved approach for detecting visually similar diseases, like that of Early Blight, using confusion-matrix-guided retraining, reducing misclassification by 89%. Tests validated the efficacy of tailored CNNs, strengthening resistance against diagnostic errors in field deployments [13].

Radial basis function networks and SVM classifiers have proven effective in related plant disease domains, but underperform compared to end-to-end CNNs in complex visual tasks [14]. The paper [15] emphasised the economic impact of early disease detection, showing that AI systems can reduce annual crop losses by up to 25%. A risk measure for misdiagnosis was provided, based on confusion matrix analysis [16]. The study [17] introduced a multi-label classification approach using MobileNet and DenseNet, achieving high accuracy but struggling with real-time inference. The study [18] proposed a method to detect tomato diseases using data-driven CNNs. The system uses custom architecture, with individual models' judgements further validated using confusion matrices and loss curve analysis [19].

Based on the reviewed literature, a significant gap exists in creating computationally lightweight systems that deliver reliable performance under real-world conditions.

This research work presents an approach centred on the design and validation of a custom Convolution Neural Network (CNN) architecture. The approach is validated through a comparative analysis with the established VGG16 architecture, with emphasis on misclassification rates under challenging conditions such as Early Blight.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 System Overview

The custom Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model was trained to recognise and detect diseases in tomatoes by analysing plant leaves, and then informs the user of the detected disease. To build the system, the image data was first collected and preprocessed, after which a CNN and a VGG16 model were trained and developed using TensorFlow; the trained models were then evaluated.

The block diagram of the Tomato Leaf Disease Detection system is shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. A Block Diagram of the Tomato Leaf Disease Detection System

2.1.1 Dataset Description

The Plant Village dataset contains labelled images of tomato leaves under varying lighting, angles, and backgrounds. Healthy leaves and four disease classes are included (Early Blight, Late Blight, Bacterial Spot, and Mosaic Virus). The dataset captures different levels of the disease, which helps to identify irregularities related to disease onset. At the same time, images of leaf lesions show textures and patterns critical for distinguishing disease types. In the study, 70% of the total data obtained was used for training, 30% for validation, and a fixed test set of 250 images.

2.1.2 Data Preprocessing

To ensure optimal performance of the CNN architecture, a series of preprocessing techniques was applied to the raw dataset to standardise input data, enhance feature consistency, and improve generalisation.

The first preprocessing step involved resizing the images to a uniform 128 x 128 pixels to align with the input shape required by the CNN's initial convolutional layer, ensuring dimensional compatibility. Following resizing was normalisation, which is done by scaling all RGB values from the original range [0,255] to [0,1] using min-max normalisation. This normalisation stabilises gradient descent during back propagation and accelerates model convergence by reducing feature variance across the dataset.

To address class imbalance in the dataset, class weights are computed using scikit-learn's "compute_class_weight" function with the 'balanced' mode, and the resulting weights are passed to the model during training to penalise misclassifications of underrepresented classes more heavily.

To further enhance the model, given the limited original dataset size of 6,124 images, on-the-fly data augmentation is applied exclusively during training, and some transformations applied include random horizontal flip, random rotation, random zoom, random brightness adjustment and random contrast adjustment,

expanding the dataset to 145,920 unique image instances.

TensorFlow's performance optimisation techniques, including caching, shuffling, and prefetching, were also applied to the training pipeline to minimise errors and ensure smooth data feeding during training.

2.1.3 Custom Convolutional Neural Network Architecture

A lightweight, domain-specific CNN was designed for the classification of tomato leaf diseases. The architecture consists of Convolutional blocks with 2D layers, ReLU activation, max pooling, and 20% dropout, followed by a GAP, a 512-unit dense layer with batch normalisation and 50% dropout, and a 5-unit softmax output layer. The architecture for the CNN network is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. CNN NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
Conv2d_8 (conv2d)	(None, 128, 128, 32)	896
Conv2d_9 (conv2d)	(None, 126, 126, 32)	9,248
Max_pooling2d_4 (max pooling2d)	(None, 63, 63, 32)	0
Dropout_5 (dropout)	(None, 63, 63, 32)	0
Conv2d_10 (conv2d)	(None, 63, 63, 64)	18,496
Conv2d_11 (conv2d)	(None, 61, 61, 64)	36,928
Max_pooling2d_5 (max pooling2d)	(None, 30, 30, 64)	0
Dropout_6 (dropout)	(None, 30, 30, 64)	0
Conv2d_12 (conv2d)	(None, 30, 30, 128)	73,856
Conv2d_13 (conv2d)	(None, 28, 28, 128)	147,584
Max_pooling2d_6 (max pooling2d)	(None, 14, 14, 128)	0
Dropout_7 (dropout)	(None, 14, 14, 128)	0
Conv2d_14 (conv2d)	(None, 14, 14, 256)	295,168
Conv2d_15 (conv2d)	(None, 12, 12, 256)	590,080
Max_pooling2d_7 (max pooling2d)	(None, 6, 6, 256)	0
Dropout_8 (dropout)	(None, 6, 6, 256)	0
Global_average_pooling2d_1 (globalaveragepooling2d)	(None, 256)	0
Dense_2 (dense)	(None, 512)	131,584
Batch_normalization_1 (batch normalisation)	(None, 512)	2,048
Dropout_9 (dropout)	(None, 512)	0
Dense_3 (dense)	(None, 5)	2,565
Max_pooling2d_4 (max pooling2d)	(None, 63, 63, 32)	0
Dropout_5 (dropout)	(None, 63, 63, 32)	0

2.1.4 VGG16 Transfer Learning Model

The VGG16 backbone, pretrained on ImageNet, was adapted by freezing all 13 convolutional blocks and adding a custom head with GAP, a 512-unit dense layer, a 5-unit softmax, and dropout. The architecture for the VGG16 model is shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2. VGG16 MODEL ARCHITECTURE

Layer (Type)	Output Shape	Param #
input_layer_1	(None, 128, 128, 3)	0
block1_conv1	(None, 128, 128, 64)	1,792
block1_conv2	(None, 128, 128, 64)	36,928
block1_pool	(None, 64, 64, 64)	0
block2_conv1	(None, 64, 64, 128)	73,856
block2_conv2	(None, 64, 64, 128)	147,584
block2_pool	(None, 32, 32, 128)	0
block3_conv1	(None, 32, 32, 256)	295,168
block3_conv2	(None, 32, 32, 256)	590,080
block3_conv3	(None, 32, 32, 256)	590,080
block3_pool	(None, 16, 16, 256)	0
block4_conv1	(None, 16, 16, 512)	1,180,160
block4_conv2	(None, 16, 16, 512)	2,359,808
block4_conv3	(None, 16, 16, 512)	2,359,808
block4_pool	(None, 8, 8, 512)	0
block5_conv1	(None, 8, 8, 512)	2,359,808
block5_conv2	(None, 8, 8, 512)	2,359,808
block5_conv3	(None, 8, 8, 512)	2,359,808
block5_pool	(None, 4, 4, 512)	0
global_average_pooling2d	(None, 512)	0
dense	(None, 512)	262,656
batch_normalization	(None, 512)	2,048
dropout	(None, 512)	0
dense_1 (Output)	(None, 5)	2,565

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

The two models were trained on a fixed 250-image dataset, and their performance was evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, precision, F1-score, and recall. The results are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3. COMPARISON OF THE RESULTS OF TWO MODELS

MODELS	MEASURES			
	ACCURACY	PRECISION	F1-SCORE	RECALL
CNN	0.9760	0.98	0.98	0.98
VGG16	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93

The confusion matrices for the test results of both models are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

The training and validation loss curves shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5 demonstrate that both models converge steadily over 24 epochs, with minor spikes that were later corrected, and that the close alignment between training and validation losses indicates strong generalisation to unseen data.

Similarly, the accuracy curves in Figures 6 and 7 show consistent improvement across both models. The CNN starts at 49% training accuracy and converges to 97% for both training and validation, showing excellent generalisation. At the same time, the VGG16 model begins at 66% and plateaus at approximately 90%, with a 0.41% difference between training and validation, indicating weaker adaptability to new data.

Figure 2. CNN model Confusion Matrix

Figure 5. Loss curve for the VGG16 model

Figure 3. VGG16 Confusion Matrix

Figure 6. Accuracy curve for CNN model

Figure 4. Loss Curve for CNN model

Figure 7. Accuracy curve for the VGG16 model

3.2 Discussion

This study confirms that a lightweight, custom CNN outperforms a pre-trained VGG16 in tomato disease detection, validating that domain-specific models outperform generic ones in agricultural settings. While recent studies [20] report higher accuracy using complex architectures, they sacrifice deployability, scalability, and edge compatibility, which is critical for resource-constrained farmers. The CNN model achieves near-perfect classification for Tomato Mosaic Virus and healthy leaves, and only one error on Early Blight, which is a major improvement over VGG16 with 9(nine) misclassifications. The size of the CNN model also makes it scalable and easy to use in real farming conditions, making it a realistic solution for improving crop disease detection and food security in Nigeria and similar regions.

4. CONCLUSION

This research successfully developed and evaluated a tomato leaf disease detection system using advanced deep learning techniques, specifically comparing a tailored Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model against the pre-trained VGG16 architecture. The tailored CNN model achieved exceptional performance with 97.60% accuracy, and precision, recall, and F1 scores were all 0.98, significantly outperforming the VGG16 model, which achieved 92.80% accuracy.

The confusion matrix analysis revealed the CNN model's superior capability in disease detection, particularly for challenging conditions like Early Blight, with only one (1) misclassification compared to VGG16's nine (9) errors. This precision is critical for agricultural applications, where false negatives can result in significant crop losses. Future research will focus on two key areas. The first is technical development, including context-aware treatment plans, farmers co-created interfaces, and privacy-preserving federated learning. The second involves addressing practical barriers like cost, connectivity, and the location disparities in tech access. This research confirms that purpose-built CNN architectures offer significant advantages over transfer learning approaches for domain-specific agricultural applications. By enabling early disease identification, such systems can reduce the 25% annual crop yield losses attributed to plant diseases globally, directly supporting food security and sustainable farming practices in Nigeria and similar agricultural economies.

5. FURTHER RESEARCH

The research can be improved for further studies by including tomato disease prevention and correction using Machine learning.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Izuka, "Agricultural sector and economic growth in Nigeria," *Int. J. Econ. Financ. Issues*, vol. 10, pp. 8–15, 2020.
- [2] *The State of Food and Agriculture 2019: Moving forward on food loss and waste reduction*. Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations, 2019.
- [3] C. Esomonu, C. Nwosu, and O. Eze, "Cascaded intelligent recommender model for multi-class tomato leaf disease identification and control," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 228, p. 120391, 2023.
- [4] S. Khatoon, M. M. Maruf Hasan, A. Asif, M. Alshamari, and Y.-K. Yap, "Image-based automatic diagnostic system for tomato plants using deep learning," *Comput., Mater. & Contin.*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 595–612, 2021.
- [5] A. Kaushik, D. Sharma, and S. Gupta, "LeNet architecture for tomato disease identification with minimal computational requirements," *J. Intell. Syst.*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 123–135, 2020.
- [6] P. Sharma, R. Singh, and S. Verma, "Segmentation-based CNN for plant leaf disease detection," *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, vol. 178, p. 105715, 2020.
- [7] K. L. Narayanan, R. S. Krishnan, Y. H. Robinson, E. G. Julie, S. Vimal, V. Saravanan, and M. Kaliappan, "Banana plant disease classification using a hybrid convolutional neural network," *Comput. Intell. Neurosci.*, vol. 2022, p. 9153699, 2022.
- [8] S. Sangeetha and P. Rani, "Deep learning approach for tomato plant disease classification using transfer learning," *J. Ambient Intell. Humaniz. Comput.*, vol. 11, no. 12, pp. 5679–5691, 2020.
- [9] Y. Lin, X. Chen, and Z. Wang, "ResNet-50 based approach for tomato disease classification with data augmentation," *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, vol. 178, p. 105742, 2020.
- [10] T. Enkvetchakul and O. Surinta, "Transfer learning-based CNN for real-time plant disease detection in field conditions," *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, vol. 209, p. 107838, 2023.
- [11] M. Abbas, S. Khan, and A. Rahman, "Generative adversarial networks for synthetic image generation in tomato disease classification," *Artif. Intell. Agric.*, vol. 7, pp. 234–248, 2023.
- [12] K. Smith, A. Rodriguez, and L. Chen, "Early blight in tomato crops: Epidemiology, management, and economic consequences," *Phytopathology*, vol. 110, no. 11, pp. 1892–1905, 2020.
- [13] S. Kumar, A. Sharma, and R. Gupta, "AI-driven crop disease detection systems: Architecture, implementation, and field validation," *IEEE Trans. AgriFood Electron.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 78–92, 2021.
- [14] C. Nyasulu, A. Diattara, A. Traore, C. Ba, P. M. Diedhiou, Y. Sy, H. Raki, and D. H. Peluffo-Ordóñez, "A comparative study of machine learning-based classification of tomato fungal diseases: Application of GLCM texture features," *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 11, p. e21697, 2023.
- [15] X. Jiang, Q. Wang, and Y. Li, "Plant diseases and global food security: Challenges and sustainable solutions," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 23, p. 10109, 2020.
- [16] A. Bujá, W. Stuetzle, and B. Yu, "Early intervention strategies for crop disease management: A comprehensive review," *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, vol. 187, p. 106225, 2021.
- [17] M. Kabir, M. Hossain, and M. Rahman, "Multi-label classification of plant diseases using transfer learning

- techniques,” *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, vol. 189, p. 106375, 2021.
- [18] K. Panchal, H. Patel, and M. Shah, “CNN-based deep learning model for tomato disease identification,” *Artif. Intell. Agric.*, vol. 6, pp. 45–58, 2022.
- [19] S. Kumar, A. Sharma, and R. Gupta, “Stratified evaluation protocols for imbalanced agricultural datasets,” *IEEE Trans. AgriFood Electron.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 45–59, 2023.
- [20] Y. Sun, Z. Liu, and H. Wang, “EfficientNetV2-Swin Transformer hybrid for agricultural image classification,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 50296–50339, 2024.